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Optimal Control with Exponential Decay Rate for Air-to-Air Missile System

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Abstract

The optimal control with exponential decay rate problem of the air-to-air missile system is studied. A nonlinear, coupling and uncertain dynamic model of the air-to-air missile with six degrees of freedom is considered. Because it is difficult to design the controller for the air-to-air missile control system, the nonlinear and coupling uncertain control system is simplified, and a linear model is obtained. Then, based on optimal control approach, an optimal controller with exponential decay rate is designed for the air-to-air missile. Numerical simulations illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed controller.

Keywords: *Optimal control, Air-to-air missile, Nonlinear system.*

1. Introduction

In the future air combat, the missile must have strong maneuverability and off-axis emissive capability and all range attack ability, especially rear hemisphere attacking target ability. Therefore, the air-to-air missile in the future should have huge off-axis capability and the better maneuverability and agility.

In recent years, due to the fast response, insensitivity to system parameters and external disturbances, algorithm simpleness and strong robustness, optimal control has attracted much attention in the integrated design of guidance and control. Shtessel et al. studied the integrated guidance and control problem based on first order, two order and higher order sliding mode control [1-3]. Shima and Idan et al. [4-6] established the direct connection between the control input and the control target with the zero miss distance as the sliding surface, and design the integrated controller. Nathan et al. [7-8] took the predicted collision point error as the sliding mode surface, and use the finite time convergence of the sliding mode state to meet the required constraints, and propose an integrated sliding mode control method.

In this paper, the optimal control with exponential decay rate problem of the air-to-air missile system is studied. A nonlinear, coupling and uncertain dynamic model of the air-to-air missile with six degrees of freedom is considered. Because it is difficult to design the controller for the air-to-air missile control system, the nonlinear and coupling uncertain control system is simplified, and a linear model is obtained. Then, based on optimal control approach, an optimal controller with exponential decay rate is designed for the air-to-air missile. Numerical simulations illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed controller.

2. Mechanical Model and Dynamical System

The research object of this paper is the air-to-air missile that uses aerodynamic layout with aerodynamic force / thrust vector composite control system, and in the active phase can use thrust vector control rudder or air rudder. Because the aerodynamic configuration of the missile uses normal pneumatic layout, so the aerodynamic characteristics of the missile rudder is simple. Considering this characteristic, the aerodynamic contribution of the air rudder is simply considered as a linear function of the rudder deflection angle. In addition, the influence of aerodynamic torsion angle on aerodynamic forces can be neglected without considering the aerodynamic coupling characteristics at high angles of attack.

Based on the above considerations, in order to make the motion equation of the missile with six degrees of freedom not too complex, the following assumptions should be made:

- 1) The elastic mode of the missile is neglected, and the missile is considered as a rigid body;
- 2) Assuming that the thrust force of the engine is constant, and the force provided by the thrust vector deflection is only involved in the longitudinal and lateral motions of the missile. Thrust vector control actuator model assuming it thrust size is constant and assuming that only in the pitch and yaw plane surface deflection of thrust vector, and use two kinds of actuator to complete the two deflection (not from the rolling control system);
- 3) Ignoring the influence of gravity, considering only the action force and thrust force of the control force and thrust vector, and the influence of gravity can easily be compensated;
- 4) Due to the short time of compound control turn, the missile is considered to be in short period motion, and the missile, rotation inertia and velocity are considered constant;
- 5) The center of mass of missile remains unchanged.

The aerodynamic force / thrust vector composite control system of the missile is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \dot{\alpha} &= \omega_z - \omega_x \tan \beta \cos \alpha + \omega_y \tan \beta \sin \alpha - \frac{qS(C_n^\alpha \alpha + C_n^{\delta_z} \delta_z) \cos \alpha}{mV \cos \beta} \\
 &\quad + \frac{qS \sin \alpha}{mV \cos \beta} C_x - \frac{P \sin \alpha}{mV \cos \beta} + \frac{P \delta_{pz} \cos \alpha}{mV \cos \beta} \\
 \dot{\beta} &= \omega_x \sin \alpha + \omega_y \cos \alpha + \frac{qS \cos \alpha \sin \beta}{mV} C_x - \frac{P \cos \alpha \sin \beta}{mV} + \\
 &\quad \frac{qS(C_n^\alpha \alpha + C_n^{\delta_z} \delta_z) \sin \alpha \sin \beta}{mV} + \frac{qS(C_z^\beta \beta + C_z^{\delta_\gamma} \delta_\gamma) \cos \alpha}{mV} + \\
 &\quad \frac{P \delta_{pz} \sin \alpha \sin \beta}{mV} + \frac{P \delta_{p\gamma} \cos \alpha}{mV} \tag{1} \\
 \dot{\gamma} &= \omega_x \\
 \dot{\omega}_x &= \frac{(m_x^{\bar{\omega}_x} \frac{\omega_x L}{V} + m_x^{\delta_x} \delta_x) qSL}{J_x} \\
 \dot{\omega}_\gamma &= \frac{m_\gamma^{\bar{\omega}_\gamma} \omega_\gamma L}{V J_\gamma} + \frac{(m_\gamma^{\delta_\gamma} \delta_\gamma + m_\gamma^\beta \beta) qSL}{J_\gamma} + \frac{(J_z - J_x) \omega_z \omega_x - lP \delta_{\gamma z}}{J_\gamma} \\
 \dot{\omega}_z &= \frac{m_z^{\bar{\omega}_z} \omega_z L}{V J_z} + \frac{(m_z^{\delta_z} \delta_z + m_z^\alpha \alpha) qSL}{J_z} + \frac{(J_x - J_\gamma) \omega_\gamma \omega_x - lP \delta_{z\gamma}}{J_z}
 \end{aligned}$$

in which, α, β, γ are attack angle, sideslip angle and roll angle, respectively; and $\omega_x, \omega_\gamma, \omega_z$ are relevant rotational angular rates respectively; q is dynamic head; S is characteristic area, L is characteristic length, P is engine thrust force, m is missile mass, V is missile velocity, J_i ($i = x, \gamma, z$) are projections of the missile inertia tensor on x, γ, z axes, δ_i ($i = x, \gamma, z$) are relevant rudder deflection angles, C_i^j are relevant aerodynamic coefficients, m_i^j are relevant aerodynamic moments.

It can be seen from (1) that the air-to-air missile control system model with six degrees of freedom has complex nonlinear and coupling characteristics. When considering gust disturbance, it also involves uncertainties, which makes the design of control system more difficult. In practical design, the model needs to be simplified. The usual practice is to assume that the missile does not roll during the target pursuit, and the three-dimensional interception problem is decomposed into two dimensional interception problems in the longitudinal and lateral planes.

Based on the assumptions following:

- 1) The missile body does not roll;
- 2) The angle of attack and the sideslip angle of the missile are smaller;
- 3) The coupling term for the rest of the channel is bounded and unknown.

The approximate linear model is proposed in [9] as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\ddot{\varepsilon} &= -\frac{2\dot{R}}{R}\dot{\varepsilon} - \frac{57.3qSC_\gamma^\alpha + P}{mR} + \Delta_\varepsilon, \\ \dot{\alpha} &= -\frac{57.3qSC_\gamma^\alpha + P}{mV}\alpha + \omega_z + \Delta_\alpha, \\ \dot{\omega}_z &= \frac{57.3qSLm_z^\alpha}{J_z}\alpha + \frac{qSL^2m_z^{\bar{\omega}_z}}{VJ_z}\omega_z + \frac{57.3qSLm_z^{\delta_z}}{J_z}\delta_z + \Delta_{\omega_z},\end{aligned}\tag{2}$$

in which, ε denotes the dip angle at the very moment.

Choose state variables for the air-to-air missile control system (2) in the following:

$$\begin{aligned}x &= [\dot{\varepsilon}, \alpha, \omega_z]^T \\ u &= \delta_z \\ y &= \dot{\varepsilon} = x_1\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

and the system (2) is rewritten in the state-space representation:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x} &= \begin{bmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & 0 \\ 0 & a_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{bmatrix} x + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ b_3 \end{bmatrix} u + \begin{bmatrix} \Delta_1 \\ \Delta_2 \\ \Delta_3 \end{bmatrix} \\ y &= x_1\end{aligned}\tag{4}$$

in which, $\Delta_1, \Delta_2, \Delta_3$ are bounded unknown uncertain parameters; R represents relative distance between the missile and target; and

$$\begin{aligned}
 a_{11} &= -\frac{2\dot{R}}{R}, a_{12} = -\frac{57.3qSC_{\gamma}^{\alpha} + P}{mR}, a_{22} = -\frac{57.3qSC_{\gamma}^{\alpha} + P}{mV}, \\
 a_{32} &= \frac{57.3qSLm_z^{\alpha}}{J_z}, a_{33} = \frac{qSL^2m_z^{\bar{\omega}_z}}{VJ_z}, b_3 = \frac{57.3qSLm_z^{\delta_z}}{J_z}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{5}$$

The aim of this paper is to design an appropriate controller for the uncertain control system (4), which makes the closed loop control system (4) globally uniformly asymptotic stable and the output of the closed loop control system (4) asymptotically approach zero.

3. Design of Optimal Controller

In this section, we design the optimal control law with exponential decay rate for system (4). The optimal control law with α exponential decay rate can be presented in the following theorem.

Theorem 1. Consider the optimal control problem described by system (4) with performance index (5), the optimal control law $u^*(t)$ exists and is unique. Its form is as follows:

$$u^*(t) = -R^{-1}B^T P_1 x(t), \tag{6}$$

where P_1 is the unique positive definite solution of the following Riccati matrix equation:

$$(A + \alpha I)^T P_1 + P_1(A + \alpha I) - P_1 S P_1 + Q = 0. \tag{7}$$

Proof. Introduce model transform for the system (4) with performance index (5):

$$\tilde{x} = xe^{\alpha t}, \tilde{u} = ue^{\alpha t}. \tag{8}$$

and

$$\tilde{A} = A + \alpha I, \tilde{B} = B. \tag{9}$$

then, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \dot{\tilde{x}} &= \dot{x}e^{\alpha t} + \alpha xe^{\alpha t} \\
 &= Axe^{\alpha t} + \alpha xe^{\alpha t} + Bue^{\alpha t} \\
 &= \tilde{A}\tilde{x} + \tilde{B}\tilde{u}.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{10}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 J &= \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T e^{2\alpha t} [x^T(t)Qx(t) + u^T(t)Ru(t)] dt \\
 &= \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T [(xe^{\alpha t})^T Q(xe^{\alpha t}) + (ue^{\alpha t})^T R(ue^{\alpha t})] dt \\
 &= \lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T [\tilde{x}^T Q\tilde{x} + \tilde{u}^T R\tilde{u}] dt.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{11}$$

Applying the maximum principle to the optimal control problem in (14) and (15), the optimal control law can be written as

$$\tilde{u}^*(t) = -R^{-1}\tilde{B}^T\tilde{\lambda}(t), \tag{12}$$

where $\tilde{\lambda}(t)$ is the solution to the following two-point boundary value problem(TPBV):

$$\begin{aligned} -\dot{\tilde{\lambda}}(t) &= Q\dot{x}(t) + A^T\tilde{\lambda}(t), \\ \dot{\tilde{x}}(t) &= A\tilde{x}(t) - R^{-1}\tilde{B}^T\tilde{\lambda}(t), \\ \tilde{x}(0) &= x_0e^{\alpha t}, \\ \tilde{\lambda}(\infty) &= 0, \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

To solve (13), let

$$\tilde{\lambda}(t) = P_1\tilde{x}(t). \tag{14}$$

Substituting the equations of (10) and (12) into the first derivatives of (14), we get

$$\dot{\tilde{\lambda}}(t) = P_1\dot{\tilde{x}}(t) = (P_1\tilde{A} - P_1SP_1)\tilde{x}(t). \tag{15}$$

From the equation (13) and the equation (14), we obtain

$$\dot{\tilde{\lambda}}(t) = -(Q + \tilde{A}^T P_1)\tilde{x}(t). \tag{16}$$

Comparing the coefficients of (15) and (16), we obtain matrix equation:

$$\tilde{A}^T P_1 + P_1\tilde{A} - P_1SP_1 + Q = 0, \tag{17}$$

Then , adding model transform (9), we can obtain

$$(A + \alpha I)^T P_1 + P_1(A + \alpha I) - P_1SP_1 + Q = 0. \tag{18}$$

In the following, we proof the existence and uniqueness of the optimal control law. In fact, it is equivalent to proof the existence and uniqueness of the matrices P_1 .

It is well known that the existence and uniqueness of the matrix P_1 .

According to the linear regulator theory, it follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Re } \lambda_i[(A + \alpha I)^T - P_1S] &< -\alpha < 0, \\ i &= 1, 2, L, n. \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Suppose that

$$\lambda_i[(A + \alpha I)^T - P_1S] = -\alpha_i + j\beta_i, \tag{20}$$

where

$$\alpha_i > 0, \beta_i \in R, j = \sqrt{-1}, \tag{21}$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_i[(A + \alpha I)^T - P_1S]^2 &= \{\lambda_i[(A + \alpha I)^T - P_1S]\}^2 \\ &= \alpha_i^2 - \beta_i^2 - j2\alpha_i\beta_i. \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

Assume that there is a certain $\lambda_i(A - SP_1)^2 = \lambda_j(-\Omega^2)$, from (20), we have a certain $\alpha_i = 0$ at least. It is contrary with $\alpha_i > 0$. Namely, $\lambda_i(A - SP_1)^2 \neq \lambda_j(-\Omega^2)$.

When the matrices P_1 are derived, $\mathcal{K}(t)$ and the optimal control law $\mathcal{U}(t)$ can be obtained from (14) and (12), respectively. According to model transform (15), the optimal control law (6) is obtained.

The proof is complete. \square

4. Numerical Experiment

Fig. 1 Dip angle rate curve

To verify the effectiveness of the integrated guidance and control law, numerical experiment is carried out for the proposed controller. The results are given in Fig.1- Fig.3.

Fig. 2 Attack angle curve

Fig. 3 Pitch angle rate curve

Our aim is to make the closed loop of the air-to-air missile control system globally uniformly asymptotic stable and the output of the closed loop control system asymptotically approach zero. It can be seen from Fig.1- Fig.3 that the proposed controller has the advantages of short interception time, little target missing. The rudder deflection angle of the missile varies smoothly throughout the flying process, the variation of the attack angle and sideslip angle is also stable, and the amplitude of the fluctuation is also small. Especially in

the near impact point, the missile's rudder angle and the angle of attack and sideslip angle without divergent trend.

Therefore, the proposed controller is efficient, real-time and robust for the air-to-air missile control system.

5. Conclusions

The optimal control with exponential decay rate problem of the air-to-air missile system is studied. A nonlinear, coupling and uncertain dynamic model of the air-to-air missile with six degrees of freedom is considered. Because it is difficult to design the controller for the air-to-air missile control system, the nonlinear and coupling uncertain control system is simplified, and a linear model is obtained. Then, based on optimal control approach, an optimal controller with exponential decay rate is designed for the air-to-air missile. Numerical simulations illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed controller.

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